

The Impact of Education and Training in Rural Communities: A Case Study of Village-Owned Enterprise (BUMDes) Financial Training in Cinangneng Village, West Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Education and training play a strategic role in strengthening community capacity and empowerment, especially in rural economic institutions such as Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes). This study aims to examine the impact of financial education and training on improving the financial management skills of BUMDes managers in Cinangneng Village, West Java, Indonesia. Using a qualitative case study approach, data were collected through observation, in-depth interviews, and analysis of participants financial records. The results show that most participants were able to prepare basic financial reports in accordance with financial reporting standards, which were introduced not only as a technical tool but also as a mechanism to strengthen transparency, trust, and collective accountability in communitybased enterprises. Participants demonstrated a better understanding of the accounting cycle, including recording daily transactions, preparing journals, recording ledgers, preparing trial balances, and reporting financial statements. However, ongoing guidance is still needed to ensure consistency and sustainability of financial practices. This study highlights the critical role of structured education and training in improving financial literacy, BUMDes accountability, and community empowerment in rural areas.

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Education, Community Empowerment, Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes), Financial Literacy, Rural Development

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INTRODUCTION

A Village-Owned Enterprise (BUMDes) is a business entity established and managed by the village government, with legal entity status. BUMDes is originated in villages through the direct participation of separate village assets (Indonesia, 2016). The main objectives of Bumdes are to manage assets, provide services, and run various businesses to improve the welfare of the village community. The complete objectives of establishing a BUMDes are contained in Permendagri Number 4 of 2015 as the basis for implementing the provisions of Article 142 of Government Regulation Number 43 of 2014 (Indonesia, 2014) concerning the Implementation Regulations of Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning the establishment of BUMDes. Villages, as autonomous areas, are granted special rights, including those related to financial management and the allocation of village funds, as well as the village development process. There are legal bases and several regulations that must be complied with in the implementation of activities and programs in BUMDes, namely Government Regulation No. 6 of 2014 concerning village funds, Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 20 of 2018 concerning guidelines for village financial management, and Minister of Villages Regulation No. 4 of 2015 concerning the establishment, administration, management and dissolution of BUMDes. With this legal basis and regulations, BUMDes must be managed properly, especially in terms of financial management (Kemendesa, 2016). BUMDes has significant implications for village development (Hilmawan et al., 2023)). First, BUMDes manages various business sectors in the village, such as trade, services, agriculture, and tourism. Second, BUMDes can improve the welfare of the community

by providing financing for village development, supporting social programs, and empowering non-productive village community groups. Third, village independence, if BUMDes is managed professionally, transparently, and accountably, can reduce dependence on outside the village. Fourth, it can create jobs from developing BUMDes units, thereby reducing unemployment in the village, so that villagers do not need to seek work in the city (Ultari, 2024)(Revida et al., 2023).

However, BUMDes has not been able to achieve its goal of providing prosperity and independence for villages. There are challenges that must be met and addressed (Kyeyune & Ntayi, 2025). First, the management capabilities of BUMDes administrators must be improved through education and training (Lestary & Hadi, 2021). BUMDes managers must understand good management practices if they want to develop their potential optimally (Fitriani et al., 2024). Second, transparency is an important issue because public funds must be managed in an open and accountable manner. Third, limited business capital is often a major obstacle in developing new business units, so creative strategies are needed to find sources of funding. Fourth, community participation is crucial to the success of BUMDes, because without the support of the village community, BUMDes will not be sustainable (Haryadi et al., 2022) (Harinurdin et al., 2025)(Rahmawati et al., 2023).

The implementation of financial education and training based on the application of financial reporting standards is introduced not only as a technical tool but also as a mechanism to strengthen transparency, trust, and collective accountability in community-based companies (Sudarlan Sudarlan, Surahman, Nurita Affan, 2025). BUMDes Financial Reporting explains the importance of systematic transaction recording to support accountability and transparency (Czech et al., 2024).

Introduction to report formats in accordance with financial reporting standards, including: 1) Financial Position Reports; 2) assets, liabilities, and equity; 3) Income Statements (revenue, operating expenses, tax expenses); 4) notes to financial statements (Bathla et al., 2024). This training and education was conducted over two days and was held at the BUMDes in Cinangneng village with the aim of determining the results, outputs, and impacts of the implementation of these activities.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method, which aims to explore in depth the process and impact of financial education and training implemented for BUMDes managers in Cinangneng Village (Saputra & Havlicek, 2025).

The research subjects were BUMDes managers and financial training participants in Cinangneng Village, totaling 15 people (consisting of 9 women and 6 men). The research location was selected purposively because the village had implemented a structured financial training program. Data collection techniques were carried out through 1. Observation during the training process, 2. In-depth interviews with participants and training facilitators, 3. Documentation studies, in the form of participants recording exercises and draft financial reports.

Figure.1. Interactive model (Sugiyono, 2013)

The data was analyzed using an interactive analysis model that included data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Data validity was maintained through source and technique triangulation (Zeho et al., 2020).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

1. Research Results

The results of the study indicate that financial education and training have a positive impact on improving participants' financial management skills in BUMDes. In general, most participants have been able to prepare simple financial reports in accordance with financial reporting standards, although they still require further guidance and the reports produced are still relatively simple. This ability shows a significant improvement compared to the conditions before the training. As shown in the following table:

Table 1. BUMDes Financial Education and Training Process

Training Stages	Materials Provided	Participant Activities	Output Produced
Introduction to Accounting	Basic concepts of BUMDes accounting	Discussion & case studies	Understanding the role of financial statements
Transaction Recording	Daily village business transactions	Manual recording exercises	Daily transaction records
General Journal Ledger	Debit–credit principles Account grouping	Journal preparation Posting to the ledger	Simple general journal Ledger per account
Balance Sheet	Account balancing	Balance sheet preparation	Opening balance sheet
Financial Statements	SAK-EMKM	Report preparation	Draft financial statements

Table 1 explains that the initial stage of training begins with an introduction to accounting, which focuses on understanding basic accounting concepts in the context of BUMDes. At this stage, participants are involved in discussions and case studies taken from actual conditions in village enterprises. Through these activities, participants begin to understand the function and role of financial reports as tools for decision-making, transparency, and accountability in village business management.

Next, in the stage record transaction, participants are introduced to various types of daily transactions that commonly occur in BUMDes businesses, such as revenue receipts, operational expenses, and wage payments. Participants practice manual recording based on real transaction examples. The output of this stage is a daily transaction record that shows that participants are able to identify and record financial transactions chronologically.

The next stage is the preparation of a general journal, which aims to strengthen participants' understanding of debit and credit principles. Participants are guided to prepare a general journal based on the transaction records that have been made previously. The result of this stage is a simple general journal that reflects the participants' ability to classify transactions into the appropriate accounts.

After understanding the general journal, the training continues with the stage of preparing the ledger. At this stage, participants learn how to group transactions into each account through the process of transferring (posting) from the general journal to the ledger. This activity produces a ledger per account, which helps participants understand the position and movement of each financial account in a more structured manner.

The next stage is the preparation of a trial balance, which aims to ensure balance between the debit and credit sides. Participants are trained to prepare a trial balance based on the closing balances from the ledger. The output of this stage is an opening trial balance, which forms the basis for the preparation of financial statements.

The final stage of the training is the preparation of financial statements with reference to the Financial Accounting Standards for Micro, Small, and Medium Entities (SAK-EMKM). At this stage, participants prepare draft financial statements that include a statement of financial position, income statement, and notes to the financial statements. The results show that most participants have been able to prepare simple financial statements independently, although further assistance is still needed to maintain consistency and accuracy in recording (Nasyiah & Nandiroh, 2021).

Table 2. Indicators of Participant Ability Improvement

Aspects of Competence	Conditions Before Training	Conditions After Training
Financial literacy	Low, unsystematic	Improved, more structured
Transaction recording	Inconsistent	Routine & classified
Understanding the accounting cycle	Limited	Understanding the flow sequentially
Report preparation	Not up to standard	Referring to SAK-EMKM
Accountability	Weak	More transparent

In Table 2, there were significant changes in various aspects of the financial management capabilities of BUMDes participants after participating in the education and training program.

These changes indicate that the training not only improved technical skills but also strengthened the accountability and transparency of village business management.

In terms of financial literacy, the conditions prior to training showed that participants' understanding was still low and unsystematic. Participants were generally unable to link financial records to decision-making and business accountability. After training, participants' financial literacy improved and became more structured, marked by a better understanding of basic financial concepts and the importance of financial reports in BUMDes management.

In terms of transaction recording, prior to the training, recording practices were inconsistent and often poorly documented. This situation had the potential to cause inaccuracies in financial data. After the training, participants began to record transactions regularly and classify them according to account type, making the village's financial flows more orderly and easier to trace.

In terms of understanding the accounting cycle, before the training, participants had limited and partial understanding, where each stage of accounting was understood separately. After the training, participants demonstrated a more comprehensive and coherent understanding of the accounting cycle, from transaction recording, journal preparation, transfer to the ledger, to the preparation of financial statements.

The ability to prepare financial statements also improved significantly. Before the training, the financial statements prepared did not refer to applicable accounting standards. After the training, participants were able to prepare financial statements with reference to SAKEMKM, so that the reports produced were more systematic, accountable, and relevant to the needs of BUMDes management.

The most significant change was seen in accountability. Before the training, weak financial recording and reporting led to low transparency in BUMDes management. After the training, improved quality of financial recording and reporting led to more transparent and accountable management, which ultimately increased public trust in BUMDes as a village economic institution.

Table 3. Village Community Empowerment Indicators

Dimensions of Empowerment	Indicators	Research Findings
Knowledge	Basic accounting understanding	Significant improvement
Skills	Financial statement preparation	Participants are able to create drafts
Attitudes	Accountability awareness	More responsible
Independence	Business management	Beginning to be independent but still need guidance
Institutional	BUMDes governance	More organized and documented

Based on the empowerment dimension table, the results of the study show that financial education and training programs have a positive impact on increasing the empowerment of BUMDes participants in various dimensions, both at the individual and institutional levels. In terms of knowledge, the training contributed to an increase in participants' understanding of basic accounting concepts. Before participating in the training, most participants did not have an adequate understanding of financial recording and reporting functions. After the training, their understanding of basic accounting improved significantly, as reflected in their ability to explain key concepts and apply them in managing village enterprise finances.

The skills dimension shows that participants were able to prepare simple financial reports. Participants not only understood the concepts theoretically, but were also able to produce draft financial reports based on existing transaction data. These findings indicate that the training successfully transferred the practical skills needed in managing BUMDes finances.

In terms of attitude, there was a positive change in participants' awareness of the importance of accountability. Participants became more responsible in recording and reporting financial activities and showed a higher commitment to transparency in business management.

This change in attitude is an important indicator of the empowerment process, as it reflects the internalization of values. In terms of attitude, there has been a positive change in participants' awareness of the importance of accountability. Participants have become more responsible in recording and reporting financial activities, and have shown a higher commitment to transparency in business management. This change in attitude is an important indicator of the empowerment process, as it reflects the internalization of good governance values.

The independence dimension shows that participants are beginning to be able to manage BUMDes businesses more independently. However, the results of the study also indicate that this independence is still in its early stages and requires further assistance to ensure the consistency and sustainability of the financial management practices that have been implemented.

In the institutional dimension, the training had an impact on improving the governance of BUMDes. Administrative and financial reporting processes became more organized and well documented. These improvements strengthened the institutional function of BUMDes as an accountable village economic entity that is trusted by the community.

Thus, this type of training not only encourages improvements in technical skills such as financial recording and reporting, but also strengthens participants' financial agency—that is, their ability to act independently in managing their economic resources. These findings are consistent with international studies that emphasize the importance of financial literacy as part of economic capacity building in rural communities and the strengthening of agricultural entrepreneurship in the modern era (Koç et al., 2025).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Education and Training as Drivers of Community Capacity Building

Education and training are widely recognized as critical mechanisms for building community capacity, especially in the context of rural development. Adult education theory emphasizes that the learning process must be contextual, problem-oriented, and directly relevant to the socio-economic realities of learners (Knowles, 2015). In the context of Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), financial education serves not only as a means of knowledge transfer, but also as a process of institutional competency building and accountability.

Capacity building refers to the process by which individuals and institutions develop the ability to perform functions, solve problems, and achieve goals in a sustainable manner (OECD, 2022). Financial training improves technical competencies such as bookkeeping, financial reporting, and decision-making, which are essential for strengthening local economic institutions (Molosiwa, 2025). When community members acquire these competencies, they gain greater control over economic resources, contributing to broader community empowerment.

2.2. Financial Literacy and Institutional Accountability

Financial literacy is a fundamental element of effective financial management, especially for micro and small businesses operating in rural areas. Financial literacy not only improves individual financial behavior but also institutional transparency and sustainability (Reddy & Wallace, 2025). In the context of BUMDes, weak financial reporting systems often lead to inefficiency, poor management, and a decline in public trust.

Previous empirical studies show that standardized accounting practices must be socialized through training to be effectively adopted in MSMEs and community enterprises, improving both transparency and accountability. The adoption of a standard accounting framework, such as the Financial Accounting Standards for Micro, Small, and Medium Entities (SAK-EMKM), provides a practical path to improving accountability. Although initially designed for MSMEs, SAK-EMKM is appropriate for the operational scale of BUMDes.

Training focused on the practical application of these standards enables BUMDes managers to institutionalize transparent financial practices, thereby strengthening governance structures at the village level (Karnasi et al., 2025).

2.3. Community Empowerment Perspective

Community empowerment is understood as a multidimensional process that includes increasing knowledge, skills, self-confidence, and participation in decision-making processes (Chambers, 1997). Empowerment is not an instant result, but rather a gradual transformation driven by continuous learning and institutional support.

From this perspective, financial training serves as an empowerment tool by enabling community members to actively manage economic activities rather than remain passive beneficiaries of development programs. The framework adopted in this study places education and training as the main input, financial capacity building as an intermediate outcome, and community empowerment as a long-term impact.

3. RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the theoretical perspective above, this study proposes a conceptual framework in

Education & Training → Financial Capacity → Institutional Accountability → Community Empowerment

which education and training influence financial management capacity, which in turn enhances institutional accountability and community empowerment in BUMDes.

This framework highlights the transformative role of adult education in rural economic governance (Scoones, 2023) and provides an analytical lens for interpreting empirical findings.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. The Impact of Financial Training on Participants' Financial Management Skills

The results of this study indicate that financial education and training significantly improve participants' understanding of the accounting cycle (Rahmawati et al., 2023), including recording daily transactions, preparing journals, recording ledgers, preparing trial balances, and financial reporting in accordance with SAK-EMKM. These results are in line with previous studies that emphasize the effectiveness of contextual and practice-based financial education in improving financial management skills among small business entrepreneurs (Hidalgomayorga et al., 2025).

The participants' ability to produce draft financial reports represents a critical shift from informal and inconsistent bookkeeping practices to more structured financial management (Is et al., 2025). This transition reflects not only the mastery of technical skills but also an increased cognitive awareness of the importance of financial accountability in BUMDes operations (Gangal et al., 2019).

4.2. Education and Training as a Pathway to Institutional Accountability

This study shows that education and training contribute directly to strengthening institutional accountability in BUMDes. Improved financial reporting practices increase transparency, enabling stakeholders—including village governments and community members—to monitor financial performance more effectively. These findings are in line with the OECD (OECD, 2022), which highlights financial capacity building as a key pillar of good governance in community-based institutions.

However, the findings also show that technical competence alone is not sufficient to ensure sustainable accountability. Although skills have improved, participants still need ongoing guidance to maintain consistency in financial recording. This shows that accountability is not only a technical issue, but also a behavioral and institutional one, which requires sustainable support mechanisms (Kyeyune & Ntayi, 2025).

4.3. Community Empowerment Outcomes in the Rural Context

From an empowerment perspective, the training program contributed to increased selfconfidence, decision-making skills, and institutional participation among participants. The ability to understand and manage financial information enabled BUMDes managers to participate more actively in the planning and evaluation process.

These outcomes resonate empowerment framework, which emphasizes control over resources and participation in decision-making as core dimensions of empowerment. In Cinangneng Village, financial training functioned as a catalyst for shifting the role of community members from passive implementers to active managers of village economic resources (Dushkova & Ivlieva, 2024).

4.4. The Need for Continuous Development and Policy Implications

Despite the positive results achieved, this study highlights the importance of continuous development to ensure long-term impact. One-time training interventions may result in shortterm skill improvements, but they are not sufficient to institutionalize financial practices. These findings reinforce the argument in the adult education literature that continuous learning and support are essential for sustainable capacity building.

From a policy perspective, integrating financial education programs with structured mentoring systems can significantly increase the effectiveness of BUMDes development initiatives. Local governments and development agencies should prioritize long-term capacity building strategies over short-term training outcomes (Ekawati & Sari, 2024).

4.5. Contribution to International Literature

This study contributes to international literature by presenting empirical evidence from the Global South context, where community-based enterprises operate under resource constraints. Unlike many studies that focus on MSMEs in urban environments, this study highlights the role of education and training in strengthening economic institutions in villages. These findings expand existing theories on community empowerment by showing how financial literacy and institutional accountability intersect in village-level enterprises (Gen Norman Thomas et al, 2024).

CONCLUSION

This study shows that education and training play an important role in improving financial management capacity and community empowerment in rural economic institutions (Zhao & Li, 2021). Through a qualitative case study of financial training for BUMDes in Cinangneng Village, the findings show that participants developed a structured understanding of the accounting cycle and were able to prepare basic financial reports in accordance with SAK-EMKM standards.

Improved financial management skills contribute to greater institutional accountability and transparency, strengthening the governance of BUMDes as village-owned enterprises (Indrawanto et al., 2025). In addition to technical competencies, this training also increases the confidence and active participation of community members in economic decision-making processes, reflecting broader empowerment outcomes (Ali et al., 2025).

However, the sustainability of these improvements is highly dependent on ongoing guidance and institutional support. Financial education initiatives should be integrated into long-term capacity building strategies rather than implemented as one-off interventions.

Overall, this study provides empirical evidence from the Global South context, reinforcing the importance of adult education and financial literacy in supporting rural development and community empowerment (Irawan, 2023)(Harinurdin et al., 2025).

Limitations and Future Research

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations that should be acknowledged.

First, the research employed a single-case study design focusing on one BUMDes in Cinangneng Village. While this approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of the training process and outcomes, the findings may not be directly generalizable to other village contexts with different institutional capacities and socio-economic conditions. Second, the study relied primarily on qualitative data collected shortly after the training program. As a result, it did not capture long-term behavioral changes or the sustainability of financial management practices over time. Future studies could adopt a longitudinal design to assess whether the skills acquired through training are consistently applied and institutionalized in BUMDes operations. Third, this research focused on participants' technical financial skills and perceived empowerment outcomes. Future research could incorporate quantitative measures, such as financial performance indicators or accountability scores, to strengthen empirical validation. Comparative studies across multiple villages or regions would also provide valuable insights into contextual factors influencing the effectiveness of financial education programs (Elva & Fitriyani, 2025).

Finally, future studies may explore the integration of digital financial tools and blended learning approaches to enhance accessibility and sustainability of financial training in rural areas (Bogdan marza, 2021). Such research would be particularly relevant in the context of increasing digitalization of village governance and economic management.

Although existing studies on financial literacy have mostly focused on micro and small enterprises in urban settings (Hosen et al., 2025), attention to community-based economic institutions in rural areas, especially in Global South countries, remains limited. This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing how continuous education and training can make a real contribution to improving financial literacy and community empowerment in a Village-Owned Enterprise (BUMDes) in Indonesia.

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